

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming & Communities Scheme

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming & Communities Scheme aimed to sustainably restore, protect and enhance water quality by developing an effective model for future catchments to foster positive relations between farmers and households.

Project Participation

Overall, 35 farmers took part, including four dairy, eight tillage and 23 drystock which covered an area over 975 hectares.

PPZ Maps

Pollution Potential Zone (PPZ) maps were scored by assessing farm conditions and management using a traffic light system. This simple, cost-effective management plan was a results-based reward scheme. Farmers designed and chose which measures to implement, with the guidance of a dedicated sustainability manager. Training was provided for local farmers and the wider community.

Results

Water protection improvement works were implemented by:

- Fencing off 15.5km of watercourses.
- Moving water troughs 20m from waterways.
- Conducting soil sampling and developing nutrient management plans for all farms.
- Placing sediment traps on farms to trap and filter run-off.
- Improving farm roadways.
- Encouraging native riparian zones and planting native hedgerows.
- Sowing winter cover crops.

Sediment trap and fencing on Irish farms

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our journey!

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